

Reproduction of Experimental Results - How Do Gain and Discount Functions Affect the Correlation between DCG and User Satisfaction?

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this report is to reproduce the experiment setup and verifying the outcomes and conclusions of the presented paper. In their analysis, Urbano and Marrero (2015)[1] investigate the ranking of a selection of discount and gain functions for DCG computation to evaluate the quality of search systems by estimating user satisfaction and preferences. After applying ANOVA tests for assessing computed bias scores, the authors' conclude that across the experiment the usage of linear gain and constant discount functions led to the lowest bias scores. In general, we were able to recreate the experimental efforts of also thanks to the efforts of the authors by providing their source code openly.

Author Keywords

Discounted Cumulative Gain, Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain, Reproducibility, ANOVA

1. INTRODUCTION

DCG (Discounted Cumulative Gain) is a metric used to measure the ranking quality of search systems. It determines whether the items suggested from a system are relevant to the customer. In case of relevancy, rewards are allocated depending on the applied gain function and which are subsequently discounted depending on their ranking in the result query and the applied discount function. The authors have analyzed 36 combinations of gain and discount functions to find the best correlated functions with user satisfaction level.

2. EXPERIMENT WORKFLOW

The experiment workflow can be summarised in Figure 1.

Assumption/(Research goal): The authors aim to evaluate the correlation between DCG and user satisfaction and how different combinations of gain and discount estimate the probabilities of user preferences between search systems.

Dataset: The data consists of 4115 preference responses provided by 113 users. Responses indicate whether (1) system A,

Figure 1. The experiment workflow

(2) system B, (3) both systems or (4) no system is considered satisfactory. In 2025 of these 4115 records, both or none of the systems were satisfactory while the remaining 2090 records preference for one of the systems.

3. REPRODUCTION WORKFLOW

Reproducibility describes the new type of structural representation of any article and recreating the abstract of the article proving the outcomes of the experiment. As the authors provide a repository containing the data and implementation of their experiment, we were able to verify their efforts and statements more conveniently and confirm that their computed results are deterministically consistent.

3.1 Analysis of the Github Repository¹ Structure

- Readme.md: describes the project (input, output data, code, how to run, license).
- Bin-folder: contains .bat and .sh files, to be executed, so they produce the desired outcome.

¹<https://github.com/julian-urbano/ecir2015-dcg>

- Config-folder: contains installation-path of R itself, which must not be executed, if the Scripts are loaded in R-Studio.
- Data-folder: File "crowd.csv" contains the main-input-data for the outcome. This will be needed to verify numbers and visualisations.
- Output-folder: contains the figures, biases and ANOVA outputs, which should be produced during code execution.
- Src-folder: contains R-Scripts and the R-Code, which will be analysed in detail.
- Template-folder: index.html demonstrate, how a query looks like.

3.2 Management and collaborative-work setup

As collaborative-platform to analyse the code and data we decided to use Deepnote. This makes it easier for us to work as a project-team, where everybody is able to contribute and see changes made by every member simultaneously. Another advantage is that Deepnote offers the possibility to run R-Code, which is the language the experiment was implemented in. The only thing necessary to make the code run was to set the environment to R 4.0 and to convert the R-scripts in the src-folder from ".R" to ".ipynb".

3.3 Test-Methodology

By adding a test-parameter for the output, a new output directory is created enabling a comparison between the original plots and results and our reproduction. The original data itself will be manipulated and stays untouched. A comparison of the output of all functions shows, that the output-data throughout the test-run is identical to the original data. To investigate the reproducibility of the experiment, we aimed to recreate all results without any changes to the setting. Additionally, we investigated the correctness of the authors statements about data characteristics, The reproduction workflow was summarised in Fig. 2.

4. RESULTS

In this section we explain which information is given in the selected paper and which measures we used to implement them. According to the selected paper, six types of variation of discount functions have been measured. These are- Zipfian discount, Linear discount, Log(2) Discount, Log (2) Discount, Log (5) Discount, and constant discount- discount.

4.1 Verifying data input

Investigating the input data by executing the code segments in RStudio debug mode iteratively, we were able to verify the data characteristics stated by the authors in the article. More specifically, a total of 4,115 records covering 432 unique queries is listed in the provided data with 2,025 and 2,090 records dedicated to the first and second part of the analysis respectively. Moreover, for each combination of gain and discount function, we can find the mentioned attribute in the data.

Figure 2. Reproduction workflow

4.2 Verifying data visualisation

As we managed to reproduce all figures listed in the selected paper, we compared and as far as we can tell, they appear to be identical. However, it should be noted that as the numbers used to create these plots were not provided by the other in the repository. Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5 show our recreation of the plots.

Figure 3. Estimated with 2025 records judging both systems as good or bad for all DCG combinations

4.3 Verifying Randomness

By applying different seed settings, we tested whether the output is prone to randomness. We did not expect any alteration of given results as neither the applied linear model nor any other part of the implementation relies on randomness. Varying seeds resulted in identical bias scores, allowing us to conclude that our expectation holds true.

Figure 4. Estimated with 2090 records judging one of the system better than the other

Figure 5. 3 different biases for each D/G-function

4.4 Verifying Portability

In order to examine the portability across operating systems, we reproduced the results on Windows (Windows 10 – Version 10.0.19043) and Linux (Debian GNU/Linux 10) machines. As we did not face any issues executing the source code, we conclude that portability is fulfilled between named operating systems. Due to limited access, we did not examine portability to macOS.

4.5 Further Investigating Parameter Robustness

By slightly altering applied input parameters, we can examine the results' sensitivity to changes in the setting as the output

partially relies on design choices for parameters. Even though falsification cannot be achieved due to the deviations from the original work, greater robustness can contribute further affirmation to the authors' presented findings. A change in the number of estimates created exactly the same bias scores. Additionally, changing the polynomial degree which also appears to be an arbitrarily set parameter (degree 2), resulted in the expected outcome creating a less linear prediction pattern. However, the created lines are still not violating the interpretations stated by the authors about function under- and overestimation.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we were not able to identify any flaw in the presented paper as the authors seem to have done the statistical analysis properly to validate their findings. However, we might suggest the inclusion of every step mentioned in the methodology in the experiment repository. More specifically, adding the implementation of the described value generation using a greedy algorithm would contribute to the completeness of the repository and improve reproducibility. Furthermore, providing the computed estimates would allow not only the visual comparison of the plots and statistical comparison of the bias scores, but also the direct comparison of those estimates. We are aware that the biases are derived from these predictions, but as these scores are mean aggregates some information might be missing.

REFERENCES

[1] Julián Urbano and Mónica Marrero. 2015. How do Gain and Discount Functions Affect the Correlation between DCG and User Satisfaction?. In *European conference on information retrieval*. Springer, 197–202.